

Examining the factors influencing the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises: the mediating role of office activities

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Abstract

Office Administration Performance (OAP) is increasingly regarded as a key factor in enhancing business efficiency, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Vietnam. However, quantitative studies on this topic remain limited. Based on the Resource-Based View (RBV), this study analyzes internal factors such as leadership style, organizational culture, technological capacity, and financial capability to examine their influence on office administration performance. At the same time, the study investigates the mediating role of OAP in the relationship with business performance. Data were collected from 54 SMEs in Vietnam and analyzed using the PLS-SEM method. The results indicate that internal factors positively affect OAP, and OAP serves as an important bridge in transforming internal resources into business outcomes. This research provides additional empirical evidence and theoretical contributions to office management in the context of emerging economies.

Keywords: *Office activities performance, firm performance, small and medium-sized enterprises, Vietnam.*

1. INTRODUCTION

For small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), the activities of the office department play a decisive role in administration, internal communication, and decision-making support. Moreover, under the current demands of digital transformation and deep international integration, the effectiveness of office activities (Office Activities Performance – OAP) is not merely supportive, but increasingly becomes a decisive factor that governs and influences the optimization of the enterprise's overall business performance (Tuyen & Minh, 2025).

Although practice has recognized the increasingly evident role of the office in enhancing the effectiveness of corporate governance, the number of studies on this subject remains quite limited. In particular, systematic quantitative approaches aimed at exploring, identifying, and supplementing the components affecting OAP are almost absent. Existing documents, materials, and studies mainly focus on assessing administrative functions or administrative reforms in the public sector, without delving into the analysis of interactive mechanisms between organizational factors and office performance in the private enterprise sector.

From a theoretical perspective, especially under the Resource-Based View (RBV), internal resources such as leadership style, financial capacity, technological level, and corporate culture environment can be considered strategic elements if they are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (Madhani, 2010). When effectively managed, these resources not only help improve the performance of office activities but also contribute to enhancing the overall performance of the enterprise.

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Based on the above-mentioned gaps, this study will focus on assessing the impact of internal organizational factors on OAP, while also examining the mediating role of OAP in the relationship between internal factors and enterprise performance. The choice to evaluate internal factors in this research is the first step toward building a solid theoretical and empirical foundation for future discoveries.

2. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

2.1. Resource-Based View (RBV)

From the perspective of the Resource-Based View (RBV), organizational performance and competitive advantage are shaped by internal resources and capabilities (Madhani, 2010). Resources that are valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and non-substitutable are considered the core foundation enabling enterprises to achieve superior performance compared to competitors. In this study, factors such as technological capability, leadership style, financial capacity, and organizational culture are regarded as strategic resources that drive OAP (Phạm Thị Diệu Linh, 2020; Tuyen & Minh, 2025). Specifically, human resources can only maximize their potential when guided by an appropriate leadership style; strong financial capacity creates the conditions for sustaining and developing administrative activities; advanced technological capability helps optimize information flows and work execution; while employee motivation and innovative capacity are strongly reinforced only when a suitable organizational culture environment exists.

According to RBV, when these resources are simultaneously developed and effectively combined, enterprises can enhance the operational efficiency of administrative activities, thereby improving overall organizational performance.

2.2. Concept of Office

Previous studies have approached the concept of “office” from various perspectives. In the public sector, the office often functions as a service unit with the capacity to support the management activities of higher-level authorities. However, in the private sector, the definition of office remains limited and lacks consistency. (Nguyễn Thành Độ, 2005) pointed out that, in a narrow sense, the office is a workspace; while in a broader sense, it is an administrative unit that supports leadership. (Phạm Thị Diệu Linh, 2012) defined the office as a type of departmental activity responsible for handling administrative tasks within the organization and ensuring the establishment of a healthy working environment. Nevertheless, this definition does not fully capture the increasingly expanding role of the office in the modern context. According to training materials from the Office Management program at the University of Cambridge and the perspective of (Zhang, 2016), the modern office is the center for communication and information coordination within the organization.

In this study, the author adopts the concept proposed by (Tuyen & Minh, 2025), where the office is defined as the unit responsible for carrying out both internal and external administrative functions, holding a central position in receiving, processing, and disseminating information to enhance organizational performance.

2.2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Leadership capability is regarded as a core factor when evaluating organizational performance or the effectiveness of its sub-units. Previous studies have demonstrated that leadership effectiveness plays a decisive role in organizational development outcomes, whether success or failure (Arham, 2014; Zainol et al., 2018). Leadership not only encourages and fosters innovation but also creates an environment where subordinates can participate in

idea generation and strengthen professional engagement. This observation is particularly relevant in the context of small enterprises, where employees frequently interact directly with managers (Simanjuntak & Pasaribu, 2023). Research by (Tubagus, 2018) also indicated that leadership style and managerial capacity strongly and decisively influence the business performance of SMEs.

For the office unit, which is directly responsible for advising, proposing, and assisting leadership, the impact of leadership style is even more evident (Nguyễn Hữu Tri, 2005). Therefore, improving OAP depends not only on employees' efforts but also on strong managerial oversight from leaders (Nguyễn Thị Hà, 2024). Evidence from previous studies affirms that leadership significantly influences the development of organizational culture (Alvesson, 2011), enhances financial capacity (Koene et al., 2002; Miloloža, 2018), and strengthens technological capability (Seyal, 2015). Positive leadership contributes to creating a supportive working environment, which in turn fosters employee motivation, job satisfaction, and adaptability to organizational changes.

Based on these arguments, this study proposes three hypotheses:

- **H1a:** Leadership has a positive influence on organizational culture.
- **H1b:** Leadership has a positive influence on technological capability.
- **H1c:** Leadership has a positive influence on financial capacity.

Office performance is improved through the direct influence of organizational culture on employees' morale, coordination, and professionalism. A strong organizational culture positively promotes open communication, creates favorable conditions for interdepartmental cooperation, minimizes errors, and improves workflows (Shahzad et al., 2012). Currently, cultural renewal and agility are essential requirements for office employees, particularly as they take on advisory and consultative roles for leadership (Lê & Trần, 2022). However, most previous studies have only examined the relationship between organizational culture and overall organizational performance, without focusing on office performance. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

- **H2:** Organizational culture has a positive influence on office performance.

Technological capability is a key factor in enhancing administrative efficiency. In the context of modern management, internal communication effectiveness and information systems need to be optimized (Bryson et al., 2014; Zhang, 2016). The implementation of "electronic offices" aims to improve productivity, reduce processing time, minimize costs, and increase flexibility in management. In the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, applying technology in office management has become an inevitable trend (Fitrio, 2024). For instance, a study at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara showed that an online office management system improved processing speed, flexibility, and information-sharing capacity (Fitrio, 2024). Yet, research on the quantitative relationship between technology and office performance remains limited. Hence, we propose the hypothesis:

- **H3:** Technological capability has a positive influence on office performance.

A strong financial capacity helps enhance organizational efficiency. Many studies have confirmed the link between financial strength and performance in SMEs (Chepkemoi et al., 2017; Exposito & Sanchis-Llopis, 2018). Enterprise stability is sustained by a solid financial foundation, which ensures employee welfare, facilitates technological infrastructure investment, and enables professional training for office staff. This is increasingly important as the office is regarded as the central hub for receiving, processing, and transmitting

information throughout the organization (Berman, 2015; Tuyen & Minh, 2025). From these arguments, we propose the hypothesis:

- **H4:** Financial capacity has a positive influence on office performance.

From the RBV perspective, the office is not merely a support unit but a strategic function that transforms internal resources into tangible outcomes at the enterprise level (Fitrio, 2024; Tuyen & Minh, 2025). Although many prior studies have examined the roles of leadership, organizational culture, technological capability, and financial strength in organizational performance, few have focused on the indirect mechanisms in which the office acts as an intermediary.

In this study, office activity performance (OAP) is proposed as a key mediating variable. Serving as the central hub for coordinating internal processes, the office performs multiple functions such as policy implementation, information management, administrative process handling, and communication support. Internal factors like effective leadership or an innovative culture can only fully deliver value when operationalized through an efficient office system. Similarly, technological and financial capacities, if not effectively coordinated in administrative operations, are unlikely to directly enhance SME performance.

Furthermore, OAP is conceptualized as a multidimensional construct comprising three core components: office personnel, information technology system management, and administrative process standardization (Tuyen & Minh, 2025). These components function both as filters and as transformation mechanisms, enabling the effective deployment of organizational capabilities.

By empirically testing the mediating role of OAP, this study aims to fill the theoretical and empirical gap in corporate governance research, while affirming that improving office performance is not only an internal objective but also a prerequisite for maximizing the value of internal resources within enterprises. Based on this, the following hypotheses are proposed:

- **H5:** Office performance has a positive influence on enterprise performance.
- **H6:** Office performance mediates the relationship between internal factors and enterprise performance.

Figure 1. Proposed model

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1. Sample and Data

The convenience sampling method was employed in this study due to limitations in resources and time. At the enterprise level, based on existing relationships, the survey questionnaire was distributed online to leaders and employees of SMEs in the Hanoi area. To improve the response rate, each questionnaire was accompanied by an introduction letter clarifying the purpose and content of the study. At the same time, the researcher guaranteed that all collected data would remain confidential and would not be used for any purposes other than academic research.

To ensure data quality under convenience sampling, the research team established three screening criteria:

1. The enterprise must be classified as small or medium-sized under current regulations.
2. The enterprise must have a dedicated administrative–human resources unit or office department.
3. Respondents must have at least two years of work experience within the same enterprise to ensure accurate reflection of the organization’s actual situation.

The survey was conducted from November 2024 to May 2025. Each enterprise was given five questionnaires (a total of 54 enterprises). As a result, 260 responses were collected, of which 209 valid responses were used for analysis. The research sample is described in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Total Responses (N = 209)		
Gender		
Male	125	59.81
Female	84	40.19
Age		
20–30	23	11.00
31–40	54	25.84
41–50	71	33.97
Above 50	61	29.19
Total Enterprises (N = 54)		
Enterprise Size		
Small enterprises	14	25.93
Medium enterprises	40	74.07
Field of Operation		
Finance	9	16.67
Manufacturing	17	31.48
Agriculture	8	14.81
Services	5	9.26
Others	15	27.78

3.2. Scale Development and Questionnaire

To ensure measurement reliability, this study employed scales previously established in the literature, with adjustments made to fit the specific context of office management in Vietnam. Specifically, the leadership style scale consists of 4 observed variables, adapted from (Chowdhury et al., 2022). The organizational culture scale consists of 4 items, adjusted from (Gelhard & Von Delft, 2016). The technological capability scale includes 6 items, adapted from (Samad, 2022). The financial capacity scale includes 8 items, refined from (Agyapong & Tweneboah, 2023). The office activity performance (OAP) scale comprises 11 items, based on (Tuyen & Minh, 2025). Finally, the enterprise performance scale contains 6 items, adapted from (Le, 2023). All scales used a 5-point Likert format, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

To maintain scale consistency, the authors followed a standardization process. Initially, the scales were translated into Vietnamese independently by two language experts, then compared and refined to ensure semantic and content equivalence. The Vietnamese version was subsequently reviewed and adjusted by administrative-office experts to ensure contextual relevance for Vietnamese enterprises. Finally, the questionnaire was pilot-tested with a small group of respondents to check clarity, comprehensibility, and usability, with adjustments made before the official survey distribution.

3.3. Data Analysis

Research data were analyzed using the PLS-SEM model with SmartPLS 4 software, following a two-step procedure. First, the measurement model was evaluated for reliability (outer loadings > 0.70 ; Cronbach's Alpha and CR > 0.70), convergent validity (AVE > 0.50), and discriminant validity (Fornell-Larcker criterion, HTMT < 0.85). Second, the structural model was estimated by testing multicollinearity (VIF < 5), estimating path coefficients through bootstrapping (1,000 samples), and analyzing the mediating effect of office activity performance (OAP) in the relationship between organizational factors and enterprise performance.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Model Reliability

Through the measurement model assessment, the scales were confirmed to ensure both reliability and convergent validity. The Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability indices were all recorded above 0.70, indicating a high degree of internal consistency among the observed variables within each construct. In addition, all AVE values exceeded 0.50, demonstrating that the criterion for convergent validity was satisfied.

The factor loadings of the observed variables were mostly above the threshold of 0.70, reflecting good representation of the latent constructs. Overall, these results indicate that the measurement model is of good quality, allowing further analysis of the structural model in the next step (Table 2).

Table 2. Structural Model

Construct	Item	Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
Financial Capacity (FC)	FC1	0.895	0.908	0.926	0.610
	FC2	0.763			
	FC3	0.785			
	FC4	0.754			
	FC5	0.774			
	FC6	0.774			
	FC7	0.789			
	FC8	0.703			
Firm Performance (FP)	FP1	0.870	0.895	0.920	0.660
	FP2	0.851			
	FP3	0.873			
	FP4	0.802			
	FP5	0.703			
	FP6	0.760			
Leadership (LS)	LS1	0.856	0.891	0.925	0.754
	LS2	0.894			
	LS3	0.878			
	LS4	0.845			
Office Activity Performance (OAP)	OAP1	0.724	0.930	0.940	0.590
	OAP2	0.784			
	OAP3	0.754			
	OAP4	0.852			
	OAP5	0.807			
	OAP6	0.772			
	OAP7	0.770			
	OAP8	0.742			
	OAP9	0.741			
	OAP10	0.771			
	OAP11	0.720			
Organizational Culture (OC)	OC1	0.850	0.904	0.933	0.778
	OC2	0.928			
	OC3	0.860			
	OC4	0.888			
Technological Capability (TC)	TC1	0.788	0.872	0.904	0.611
	TC2	0.798			
	TC3	0.836			
	TC4	0.743			
	TC5	0.725			
	TC6	0.796			

The discriminant validity of the constructs in the model is presented in Table 3 (Fornell–Larcker criterion). The square root of the AVE for each construct was greater than its correlations with other constructs, confirming that all variables satisfied the Fornell–Larcker criterion.

Specifically, the square root of AVE for each construct—Financial Capacity (0.781), Firm Performance (0.812), Leadership Style (0.869), Office Activity Performance (0.768), Organizational Culture (0.882), and Technological Capability (0.782)—was higher than the correlation coefficients between that construct and others in the research model. This indicates that the constructs were measured distinctly, without content overlap, thereby confirming that the measurement model demonstrates good discriminant validity.

Table 3. Fornell–Larcker Matrix

	FC	FP	LS	OAP	OC	TC
FC	0.781					
FP	0.542	0.812				
LS	0.572	0.407	0.869			
OAP	0.615	0.741	0.505	0.768		
OC	0.489	0.628	0.477	0.608	0.882	
TC	0.542	0.610	0.450	0.609	0.615	0.782

4.2. Hypothesis Testing

The results of the structural model assessment (see Table 4) show that all proposed hypotheses (from H1a to H5) were supported, with path coefficients significant at the 0.05 level or below. Specifically, Leadership (LS) had strong and positive effects on three key organizational factors: Organizational Culture (OC) with a coefficient of 0.477 (T = 8.595, p < 0.001), Technological Capability (TC) with a coefficient of 0.450 (T = 8.117, p < 0.001), and Financial Capacity (FC) with the highest coefficient of 0.572 (T = 11.887, p < 0.001). These relationships exhibited medium to large effect sizes (f² ranging from 0.254 to 0.486).

In addition, the internal factors OC, TC, and FC all showed positive effects on Office Activity Performance (OAP), with coefficients of 0.237, 0.177, and 0.219 respectively (all p < 0.01), and small to medium effect sizes (f² ranging from 0.041 to 0.080).

Most notably, OAP demonstrated a very strong and significant effect on Firm Performance (FP), with a path coefficient of 0.741 (T = 26.174, p < 0.001) and a large effect size (f² = 1.217). Finally, all VIF values were below the threshold of 5, indicating that multicollinearity was not present in the model.

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Relationship	Coefficient	STDEV	T-Statistic	p-Value	f ²	VIF
H1a	LS → OC	0.477	0.056	8.595	0.000	0.295	1.000
H1b	LS → TC	0.450	0.055	8.117	0.000	0.254	1.000
H1c	LS → FC	0.572	0.048	11.887	0.000	0.486	1.000
H2	OC → OAP	0.237	0.061	3.863	0.000	0.080	1.753
H3	TC → OAP	0.177	0.064	2.778	0.006	0.041	1.906
H4	FC → OAP	0.219	0.060	3.683	0.000	0.069	1.734
H5	OAP → FP	0.741	0.028	26.174	0.000	1.217	1.000

4.3. Mediation Testing

Table 5 reports the mediation testing results of Office Activity Performance (OAP). The findings indicate that all indirect relationships between internal factors and firm performance are statistically significant. Specifically, Financial Capacity affected Firm Performance indirectly through OAP, with an indirect effect of 0.163 ($T = 3.582, p = 0.000$). Similarly, Organizational Culture influenced Firm Performance indirectly through OAP, with an indirect effect of 0.176 ($T = 3.843, p = 0.000$). In addition, Technological Capability also showed a significant indirect effect, with a coefficient of 0.131 ($T = 2.730, p = 0.007$).

All these relationships had p -values below 0.01, indicating high significance and confirming that OAP plays a critical mediating role in transforming internal resources into positive business outcomes for enterprises.

Table 5. Mediation Testing Results

Hypothesis	Relationship	Coefficient	STDEV	T-Statistic	p-Value
H6	FC → OAP → FP	0.163	0.045	3.582	0.000
	OC → OAP → FP	0.176	0.046	3.843	0.000
	TC → OAP → FP	0.131	0.048	2.730	0.007

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

5.1. Discussion of Findings

The results highlight the critical role of internal factors in enhancing both office activity performance (OAP) and overall firm performance. Among them, leadership style was identified as the initiating factor, strongly influencing the development of key internal resources such as organizational culture, financial capacity, and technological capability. This finding aligns with the Resource-Based View (RBV), which posits that leadership, finance, technology, and culture constitute the foundation for building sustainable competitive advantage.

The results also demonstrate that organizational culture, financial capacity, and technological capability all have positive effects on OAP. Although their impacts differ in magnitude, all three factors play an important role in fostering internal coordination, improving administrative processes, and optimizing communication flows within the enterprise. This reflects current practice in which the office functions not merely as an administrative support unit but as a strategic coordination and communication hub.

A novel contribution of this study is the identification of the mediating role of OAP in the relationship between internal resources and firm performance. While prior studies primarily examined the direct effects of finance, culture, or technology on business outcomes, this research affirms that these resources fully realize their value only when channeled through an effectively functioning office system.

Thus, the office is not viewed as a purely administrative unit, but as a strategic link responsible for coordinating, processing, and disseminating resources across the organization. Through this role, financial, technological, and cultural capacities are translated into management practices, internal communications, decision-making support, and cross-departmental collaboration. This perspective contrasts with traditional views of the office as solely administrative, and represents a new approach to organizational management.

The study further provides empirical evidence confirming that investment in office resources—personnel, processes, and technology—is a necessary condition for maximizing

the value of organizational resources. Without effective office operations, even abundant internal resources cannot generate superior business performance.

From these findings, the study both reinforces RBV and extends its application to the mediating role of the office in modern management—an aspect that has received little attention to date. This constitutes an important theoretical contribution with both conceptual and practical significance.

5.2. Theoretical Implications

The results expand and deepen the RBV by applying it to office management—an area rarely examined from a strategic perspective. According to RBV, competitive advantage and organizational performance are built on resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable. This study demonstrates that office-related resources—financial, technological, cultural, and especially OAP—can meet these criteria when properly organized and managed. Furthermore, the study extends the application of RBV beyond core functions such as production and marketing, confirming its relevance to administrative support activities. Demonstrating that office-related internal resources can serve as foundations of competitive advantage opens a new research avenue for RBV in organizational management. It also suggests that managers should recognize the office as a strategic resource in planning and implementing long-term development strategies.

5.3. Managerial Implications

The results indicate that internal resources such as leadership style, technological capability, financial capacity, and organizational culture are decisive in improving OAP, thereby contributing to overall firm performance. Managers of SMEs should therefore adopt strategies to leverage these factors effectively.

- **Leadership:** Adopt a supportive and empowering leadership style that motivates and inspires employees. Transparent communication, active listening, and building a positive work environment foster engagement and enhance professionalism in office operations.
- **Technology:** Prioritize modernization of administrative infrastructure through document management systems, workflow coordination tools, and digital communication platforms. At the same time, provide office staff with digital skills training to effectively use these tools, thereby reducing manual work, optimizing processing speed, and improving coordination quality.
- **Finance:** Ensure a stable budget for office operations, including investments in technology, facilities, and staff development. Effective financial management, rational allocation, and cost control are essential to optimize resources and sustain administrative operations.
- **Organizational Culture:** Foster a collaborative, flexible, and innovative workplace environment. A culture that encourages open communication and information sharing enhances coordination, while continuous improvement initiatives help office functions adapt to changes and improve internal service quality.

6. CONCLUSION

This study provides empirical evidence on the impact of internal factors on OAP in SMEs in Vietnam. The findings show that leadership style, financial capacity, technological capability, and organizational culture all positively influence office performance. At the same time, OAP was confirmed as a critical mediator that transforms internal resources into business outcomes.

This discovery clarifies the strategic role of the office, moving beyond its traditional administrative support function to a mediating link in modern management. Investment in office personnel, processes, and technology infrastructure is a prerequisite for optimizing the value of organizational resources, thereby enhancing operational efficiency and business performance.

The study not only reinforces RBV but also extends its application to office management—a field rarely explored in previous research. Accordingly, enterprises should recognize the office as a strategic resource that must be integrated into the planning and execution of long-term development strategies.

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